

Case Report: A Rare Case of Cerebellar GliosarcomaDeepak Maini¹, Nidhi Binnani², Sunita Bika³, Simran Chodankar⁴^{1,4}Resident, Department of Pathology, SPMC, Bikaner, Rajasthan²Professor, Department of Pathology, SPMC, Bikaner, Rajasthan³Professor, Department Of Pathology, SPMC, Bikaner, Rajasthan

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Abstract:

Gliosarcoma is a rare subtype of glioblastoma multiforme. On histology it is a biphasic tumor having both glial as well as sarcomatous components. Here in we present a case of 32 year male who got admitted to our hospital with chief complaints of headache for the past one month which increased in intensity since the last 10 days with progressive loss of vision and complaints of giddiness, nausea and vomiting. CT scan and MRI were advised which revealed Approximately 47x40x28mm sized ill-defined heterogeneous lesion in the right cerebellar hemisphere causing mass effect over fourth ventricle. A provisional diagnosis of medulloblastoma was made based on imaging studies. Surgical intervention comprising Midline suboccipital craniotomy with excision of tumor was done. On histopathological examination a diagnosis of gliosarcoma was made after observing the H&E and Reticulin silver stained sections. Gliosarcoma is an aggressive tumor hence prompt and accurate diagnosis is required for better prognosis.

Keywords: Pregnancy, Rhinitis, Nasal, Physiological changes, Visual Analogue Scale.

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Introduction

Gliosarcoma is a rare and aggressive malignancy that accounts for 2-8% of all primary glioblastomas.[1] Gliosarcoma is a biphasic tumor which shares histologic characteristics with glioblastoma and soft tissue sarcoma, and has a shorter median survival and worse prognosis than other Glioblastomas. [2]

Gliosarcomas arising de novo without any previous glioblastoma multiforme diagnosis are termed primary gliosarcomas whereas those occurring after treatment of prior glioblastomas are called secondary gliosarcomas. Strobe initially reported gliosarcoma in 1895, but it wasn't until Feigen and Gross explained three patients with this cancer in detail in 1955 that the condition was widely recognized. [3,4]

It is primarily found in the frontal and temporal lobes of the cerebral hemispheres. On rare occasions, it can also be seen intraventricularly. [5] Gliosarcoma shares clinical and radiological characteristics with Glioblastoma multiforme.

It shows a preference for males aged 40-60. It conveys a dismal patient's clinical outcome, with an average survival of less than 6 months if the patient is not treated. [6]

Patient Presentation: We present to you a case of a 32-year-old male who got admitted to the

Neurosurgery department of Sardar Patel Medical College, Bikaner with chief complaints of headache for the past one month which increased in intensity since the last 10 days with progressive loss of vision associated with complaints of giddiness, nausea and vomiting.

On examination he was conscious and oriented to time place and person. There were no other sensory or motor neurological deficit. Past history and family history of the patient was not significant.

Imaging Studies**NCCT Head and MRI brain was done.**

- NCCT head revealed approximately 47x40x28mm sized ill-defined heterogeneous lesion in the right cerebellar hemisphere causing mass effect over fourth ventricle. Possibility of neoplastic etiology.
- MRI brain was Suggestive of mass lesion in the right cerebellar hemisphere – likely medulloblastoma.

Procedure Done: Patient underwent Midline suboccipital craniotomy with excision of tumor. Post-operative phase of the patient was uneventful.

Operation Notes: In the Posterior fossa 5x5cm sized grayish white tumor was seen which was

moderately vascular. Haemorrhage was also noted in the occipital region.

Biopsy and Histopathology

Gross findings: Tumor was received as multiple grey white soft tissue pieces which collectively measured 5x5 cms. The specimen was submitted entirely for histopathological examination in two blocks.

Histopathological Findings: Whole of the tissue was processed. It showed biphasic pattern comprising of tissue bits representing highly cellular areas showing pleomorphic cells with astrocytic/glial morphology. Cells had scanty cytoplasm and round to oval pleomorphic nuclei set against a neurofibrillary matrix. It also showed numerous proliferating blood vessels with prominent endothelial cells. At places the blood

vessels were of glomeruloid type with few vessels show evidence of endarteritis obliterans. Areas of haemorrhage and a few foci of necrosis were also seen.

Other tissue bits showed interlacing fascicles of elongated spindle shaped cells with elongated spindle shaped nuclei showing fibrosarcomatoid differentiation.

Reticulin silver staining was done which showed increased in reticulin fibers in the fibrosarcomatoid areas.

Diagnosis: A diagnosis of gliosarcoma grade IV was made based on the presence of both gliomatous and sarcomatous elements seen on H&E and reticulin staining, consistent with WHO classification criteria.

Figure 1: H&E stained sections shows both gliomatous and sarcomatous areas

Figure 2: H&E stained section shows sarcomatous area with spindles shaped cells arranged in whorls and intersecting fascicles

Figure 3: H&E stained section showing Glomeruloid blood vessel.

Figure 4: Reticulin silver stain shows increase in reticulin fibers in Sarcomatoid area

Discussion

Despite of differences in their microscopic appearances both gliosarcomas and glioblastoma multiformes share same clinical, epidemiological and behavioral profiles. [5] In year 2008 kozak et al published a study in which they studied 353 cases of adult gliosarcomas and 16035 cases of glioblastoma multiforme diagnosed between 1988 to 2004. Both the entities studied showed male preponderance. The most common site in their study for gliosarcoma was found out be the temporal lobe. Cerebellar gliosarcoma constituted only 1.4% of the cases studied. On the other hand glioblastoma was found to occur most commonly in frontal lobe. [2]

Regarding the pathophysiology of gliosarcoma, there is some disagreement. Certain writers proposed that the sarcomatous elements stemmed from the neoplastic conversion of hyperplastic blood vessels typically present in high-grade gliomas. [4]

A different theory that has gained traction recently suggests that both the gliosarcoma components have a monoclonal origin, with the sarcomatous component arising from aberrant mesenchymal differentiation of the malignant glioma. [7] Sarcomatous areas are rich in reticulin and can be demonstrated by using reticulin silver stain which in our case showed increased reticulin fibers.

On immunohistochemistry glial components are GFAP positive and sarcomatous areas are GFAP negative and positive for reticulin and vimentin. [6]

Conclusion

Gliosarcoma is a rare clinicopathological entity. It is a biphasic tumor with both glial and sarcomatous components. It shows male preponderance and is most commonly seen in temporal lobe. It is an aggressive tumor with poor outcomes hence it becomes even more important to diagnose it correctly and quickly so as to start the treatment promptly. Special stains like reticulin silver and immunohistochemistry plays an important part in its diagnosis.

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